

An expression of harmonic numbers using Mneimneh's binomial sum and the Pascal inversion formula

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Abstract

Recently, Mneimneh published an interesting binomial sum involving harmonic numbers, generalizing an identity previously highlighted by Paule and Schneider. The new identity was derived using probabilistic analysis. Campbell proposed afterwards two different proofs, based respectively on the Zeilberger algorithm and on beta-type integrals. In the present work, we obtain, using the Mneimneh identity combined with the Pascal inversion formula, two expressions of the harmonic numbers. The first one, which is a sum rule, involves the Lerch transcendent, and the second one, which is an explicit form, involves the Gauss hypergeometric series.

1 Introduction

Using a probabilistic analysis based on independent Bernoulli variables and permutations, Mneimneh derived the following expression [1]:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n H_k \binom{n}{k} p^k (1-p)^{n-k} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1 - (1-p)^i}{i}, \quad (1)$$

where $0 \leq p \leq 1$ and

$$H_k = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{1}{i} \quad (2)$$

is the usual i^{th} harmonic number. Relation (1) is a generalization of the known identity [2]:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n H_k \binom{n}{k} = 2^n \left(H_n - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{i 2^i} \right). \quad (3)$$

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Campbell proposed two proofs of the Mneimneh identity: the first one is based on a way of extending Zeilberger's algorithm to non-hypergeometric summands [3, 4], and the second proof is based on a beta-type integral formula [5].

In section 2, we derive, using the Mneimneh identity combined with the Pascal inversion formula, two expressions of the harmonic numbers. The first one has the form of a sum rule, in the sense that it relates an harmonic number H_n to harmonic numbers H_k with $0 \leq k \leq n-1$. It involves the Lerch transcendent. The second formula is an explicit form, and contains a finite summation over Gauss hypergeometric series ${}_2F_1$.

2 Two expressions of harmonic numbers

According to Pascal's inversion relation, if two sequences $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ and $(b_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ satisfy (see Appendix):

$$b_n = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} a_k, \quad (4)$$

then

$$a_n = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^{n-k} b_k. \quad (5)$$

The Mneimneh formula (1) can be recast into

$$\sum_{k=0}^n H_k \binom{n}{k} \left(\frac{p}{1-p} \right)^k = \frac{1}{(1-p)^n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1 - (1-p)^i}{i}. \quad (6)$$

In the present case, we take

$$a_k = \left(\frac{p}{1-p} \right)^k H_k \quad (7)$$

and

$$b_k = (1-p)^{-k} \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{1 - (1-p)^i}{i}. \quad (8)$$

Then we have

$$H_n = \frac{1}{p^n} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (p-1)^{n-k} \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{1 - (1-p)^i}{i}. \quad (9)$$

It turns out that [6]:

$$\sum_{i=1}^k \frac{1 - (1-p)^i}{i} = H_k + (1-p)^{k+1} \Phi(1-p, 1, k+1) + \log(p), \quad (10)$$

where

$$\Phi(z, s, a) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{(k+a)^s} \quad (11)$$

is the Lerch transcendent [7, 8]. We thus have

$$H_n = \frac{1}{p^n} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (p-1)^{n-k} [H_k + (1-p)^{k+1} \Phi(1-p, 1, k+1) + \log(p)]. \quad (12)$$

One has also, interchanging the nested summations in Eq. (9):

$$H_n = \left(\frac{1-p}{p}\right)^n \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1-(1-p)^i}{i} \sum_{k=i}^n \binom{n}{k} \frac{(-1)^{n-k}}{(1-p)^k}. \quad (13)$$

One gets easily [6]:

$$\sum_{k=i}^n \binom{n}{k} \frac{(-1)^{n-k}}{(1-p)^k} = \frac{(-1)^{n-i}}{(1-p)^i} \binom{n}{i} {}_2F_1 \left[\begin{matrix} 1, i-n \\ i+1 \end{matrix}; \frac{1}{1-p} \right], \quad (14)$$

where ${}_2F_1$ is the usual Gauss hypergeometric series. Thus, we obtain the following second expression for the harmonic number:

$$H_n = \left(\frac{1-p}{p}\right)^n \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1-(1-p)^i}{i} \frac{(-1)^{n-i}}{(1-p)^i} \binom{n}{i} {}_2F_1 \left[\begin{matrix} 1, i-n \\ i+1 \end{matrix}; \frac{1}{1-p} \right]. \quad (15)$$

We checked the formulas using the computer algebra system Mathematica [6].

3 Conclusion

In this work, we derived two identities for the harmonic numbers by combining a sum rule recently published by Mneimneh with the Pascal inversion formula. Our first form involves the Lerch transcendent, while the second is expressed in terms of the Gauss hypergeometric series ${}_2F_1$. The same methodology can be applied to the identity (7) of Ref. [5], i.e.:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n H_k \binom{n}{k} x^k y^{n-k} = (x+y)^n \left(H_n - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y^i (x+y)^{-i}}{i} \right). \quad (16)$$

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Appendix: The Pascal inversion formula

Let us proof that Eq. (4) \Rightarrow (5). We have, $\forall n \leq \mathbb{N}$:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^{n-k} \binom{n}{k} b_k = \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^{n-k} \binom{n}{k} \sum_{i=0}^k \binom{k}{i} a_i \quad (17)$$

$$= \sum_{i=0}^n \sum_{k=i}^n (-1)^{n-k} \binom{n}{k} \binom{k}{i} a_i \quad (18)$$

$$= \sum_{i=0}^n \sum_{k=i}^n (-1)^{n-k} \frac{n!}{(n-k)! i! (k-i)!} a_i \quad (19)$$

$$= \sum_{i=0}^n \sum_{k=i}^n (-1)^{n-k} \binom{n}{i} \binom{n-i}{k-i} a_i \quad (20)$$

$$= \sum_{i=0}^n \binom{n}{i} a_i \sum_{l=0}^{n-i} (-1)^{n-l-i} \binom{n-i}{l} \quad (21)$$

$$= a_n. \quad (22)$$

Now, let us prove that (5) \Rightarrow (4). One starts from

$$a_n = \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^{n-k} \binom{n}{k} b_k \quad (23)$$

i.e., setting $\forall n \leq \mathbb{N}$, $b'_n = (-1)^n a_n$ and $a'_n = (-1)^n b_n$:

$$b'_n = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} a'_k. \quad (24)$$

Then, according to (\Rightarrow):

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} a_k = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} (-1)^k b'_k = (-1)^n a'_n = b_n, \quad (25)$$

which completes the proof.